

Coordination compounds of Schiff base containing urea moiety

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Abstract : A MeOH solution of salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyphenylurea in equimolar ratio reacts and forms the Schiff base, LH₃ (1). The latter reacts with Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}, MoO₂^{II}, UO₂^{II} and Zr(OH)₂^{II} ions in MeOH and forms the corresponding coordination compounds, [Cu(LH)]₂ (2), [M(LH)(MeOH)] (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}) (3), [M'(LH)(MeOH)₂]₂ (M' = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}) (4), [FeCl(LH)(MeOH)]₂ (5), [M''O₂(LH)(MeOH)] (M'' = Mo^{VI} or U^{VI}) (6 and 7) and [Zr(OH)₂(LH)(MeOH)₂] (8) respectively. The coordination compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molecular weight, molar conductance, spectral (IR, reflectance, NMR), thermal and magnetic susceptibility measurements. 1 acts as a dibasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in 2-8. The coordination compounds 2, 4 and 5 are paramagnetic, while 3, 6, 7 and 8 are diamagnetic. A square-planar geometry to 2; a tetrahedral geometry to 3; an octahedral geometry to 4, 5, 6 and 7 and a pentagonal-bipyramidal geometry to 8 have been assigned. The energy optimized structures, 9, 10 and 11 for 1, 3 (M = Zn^{II}) and 6 respectively are proposed using the semiempirical ZINDO/1 quantum mechanical calculations.

Keywords : *o*-Hydroxyphenylurea, Schiff base, spectral studies, magnetic studies, coordination compounds.

Introduction

The Schiff bases containing O and N donor atoms are known to play important role in biological systems and represent interesting models¹. The Schiff bases and their coordination compounds have received considerable research interest because of unusual configuration² and interaction of donor sites present in these ligands giving the coordination compounds of different geometry and properties³. The coordination compounds of Schiff bases have also been studied extensively due to their various applications like catalysts, pharmaceutical agents, anti-tumor, antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral, anticonvulsive, anti-fouling and as corrosion inhibitors⁴. The molecular modeling has played an important role in the study of ligands and their complexes^{5,6}. The coordination compounds of Cu^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Ti^{IV} and Sn^{IV} ions with isomeric Schiff base (derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde and salicylhydrazide) of 1 have been reported elsewhere⁷. In

the present paper, we thought it worthwhile to synthesize and characterize some coordination compounds of 1 with Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}, MoO₂^{II}, UO₂^{II} and Zr(OH)₂^{II} ions. It is expected that the present coordination compounds may find applications in biochemical, analytical and antimicrobial field.

Results and discussion

A MeOH solution of 1 reacts with a MeOH solution of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}, MoO₂^{II}, UO₂^{II} and Zr(OH)₂^{II} ions in equimolar ratio and forms 2-8 respectively. The coordination compounds are insoluble in H₂O, MeOH and EtOH but soluble in DMF and DMSO.

(2)

(3; M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II})

(4; M' = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II})

(5)

(6)

(7)

(8)

Proposed structures of coordination compounds

The molar conductance data ($2.3\text{--}8.6\text{ mho cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ in 10^{-3} M DMF solution) reveal their non-electrolytic nature. The molecular weight measurements indicate the dimeric nature of **2**, **4** and **5**, and the monomeric nature of **3**, **6**, **7** and **8**. The thermal study of **3** ($M = \text{Zn}$) and **8** indicates the presence of coordinated MeOH in them.

The IR spectra of **1-8** were recorded in KBr pellets. **1** exhibits a strong band at 2700 cm^{-1} due to the intramolecular H-bonded phenolic OH group⁸. The coordination compounds exhibit a broad band at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band may be due to (i) coordinated MeOH molecule(s) in **3-8** and/or (ii) due to the enolization of LH_3 on coordination⁹. The presence of this band in **2** supports this. **1** occurs in keto form as evident from the presence of a band at 1669 cm^{-1} . The absence of this band and appearance of a new band at $\sim 1240\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **2-8** are indicative of enolisation on coordination and non-involvement of the carbonyl O atom in coordination. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine) stretch¹⁰ of **1** occurs at 1620 cm^{-1} . In the coordination compounds, this band shifts to lower energy by $8\text{--}22\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the coordination¹¹ through the azomethine N atom of **1**. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) stretch of **1** occurring at 1526 cm^{-1} shifts to higher energy by $\leq 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **3**, **6**, **7** and **8** and by $20\text{--}35\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **2**, **4** and **5** supporting the involvement of phenolic O atom towards coordination¹². The magnitude of the above shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) stretch indicates the presence of a monomeric structure in **3**, **6**, **7** and **8** and a dimeric structure in **2**, **4** and **5** as in the event of a dimeric structure, the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) stretch is known to shift to higher energy by $> 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The involvement of phenolic O and azomethine N atoms in coordination is further supported by the appearance of new non-ligand bands at $540\text{--}570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $420\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ stretches in **2-8**. These bands are in the order of increasing energy : $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N}) < \nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ ¹³ as expected due to the greater dipole moment change in the M-O vibration, greater electronegativity of the O atom than N atom and shorter M-O bond length than the M-N bond length¹⁴. Thus, **1** behaves as a dibasic tridentate ONO donor ligand in **2-8**. The presence of a new band at 832 cm^{-1} in **5** due to the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Fe}-\text{O}-\text{Fe})$ stretch supports the presence of an oxo-bridged structure in it¹⁵. MeOH exhibits the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (alcoholic) stretch⁹ at 1034 cm^{-1} . This band shifts to lower energy by $50\text{--}70\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **3-8** confirming the pres-

ence of coordinated MeOH⁹. The absence of a new band at $825\text{--}960\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **8** rules out the presence of the $\nu(\text{Zr}=\text{O})$ stretch and the formulation of this compound as $[\text{ZrO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]$. The presence of a new band at 1149 cm^{-1} in this compound indicates the presence of the $\delta(\text{Zr}-\text{OH})$ bending mode¹⁶ and this supports the formulation of this compound as $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and not as $[\text{ZrO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]$. Syamal and Kumar¹⁷ have developed a non-aqueous titration method for distinguishing the compounds possessing $[\text{ZrO}]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ moiety. Oxozirconium(IV) compounds react with 3 N HCl in MeOH and as a result, the oxo group gets protonated, while the zirconium(IV) compounds containing $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ moiety do not add up HCl at all. The coordination compound, $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]$ does not react with 3 N HCl in MeOH and this conclusively proves the absence of the $\text{Zr}=\text{O}$ bond in this compound. The $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ stretches occur at 935 and 910 cm^{-1} respectively in **6** and these bands occur in the usual ranges ($892\text{--}964\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $840\text{--}925\text{ cm}^{-1}$) reported for the majority of MoO_2 ^{II} coordination compounds¹⁸. The presence of the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ bands indicates the presence of the *cis*- MoO_2 structure as the compounds having *trans*- MoO_2 structure exhibit only the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ stretch since the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ stretch is IR inactive. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ stretch occurs at 905 cm^{-1} in **7** and this band occurs in the usual range ($870\text{--}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$) observed for the majority of *trans*- UO_2 ^{II} coordination compounds^{12,19}.

The nujol mull electronic spectra of **2-8** could not be recorded as these coordination compounds do not form a good mull and hence their reflectance spectra were recorded. The coordination compound **2** shows two bands one at 15650 cm^{-1} and the other at 20130 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively, indicating a square-planar arrangement around each Cu^{II} ion²⁰. The coordination compound **4** ($M' = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$) shows three bands at 16220 , 21310 and 25850 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)(\nu_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, in an octahedral environment²¹. The coordination compound **4** ($M' = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$) shows three bands at 9210 , 13550 and 19760 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, in an octahedral environment^{14,22}. The spectral parameters cal-

culated by following the standard method^{22,23} and using the free ion Racah parameter (B) value²⁴ of 971 cm^{-1} are : $v_3 : v_1$ (2.14), $10 Dq$ (10371 cm^{-1}), B' (780.7), β (0.80), B^0 (20%) and CFSE ($-99.33\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). The coordination compound **4** ($M' = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$) exhibits three bands at 9720 , 16390 and 25540 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(v_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(v_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions respectively, indicating an octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ions²². The spectral parameters calculated by following the standard method^{22,23} and using the free ion Racah parameter (B) value²⁴ of 1030 cm^{-1} are as follows : $v_2 : v_1$ (1.68), $10 Dq$ (9720 cm^{-1}), B' (799.8), β (0.77), B^0 (23%) and CFSE ($-139.65\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). The reduction of Racah parameter (from the free ion values : 971 cm^{-1} to 780.7 cm^{-1} for Co^{II} and from 1030 cm^{-1} to 799.8 cm^{-1} for Ni^{II}) and the values of % covalence in **4** (20.0% where $M' = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and 23.0% where $M' = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$) are indicative of the covalent nature of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} coordination compounds. The $10 Dq$ value of the Co^{II} coordination compound is greater than that of the corresponding Ni^{II} coordination compound : $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$, $9720\text{ cm}^{-1} < [\text{Co}(\text{LH})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$, 10371 cm^{-1} . This is in line with the spectrochemical series of metal ions for a given ligand, given stoichiometry and a given stereochemistry²⁵ : $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$. The B^0 value of the Ni^{II} coordination compound is comparable to that of the corresponding Co^{II} coordination compound : $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$, 23% \sim $[\text{Co}(\text{LH})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$, 20%. This is in line with the nephelauxetic metal ion series in terms of B and B^0 for a given ligand, given stoichiometry and a given stereochemistry²⁶. The higher negative CFSE value in the Ni^{II} coordination compound in comparison to that of the corresponding Co^{II} coordination compound is as expected. The coordination compound **5** exhibits three bands at 12000 , 15650 and 19000 cm^{-1} corresponding to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)(v_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)(v_2)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)(v_3)$ transitions respectively in octahedral symmetry²⁷.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of **1** and **3** ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) have been recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. The chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm downfield from TMS²⁸. The Schiff base **1** exhibits a multiplet at δ 6.82–8.00 ppm due to the aromatic protons, a singlet at δ 7.32 ppm due to the azomethine proton, a broad signal at δ 10.91 ppm due to the phenolic proton and a singlet at δ 11.73 ppm due to the N–H proton. MeOH exhibits the signal due to the

alcoholic proton at δ 4.84 ppm and the methyl protons at δ 3.35 ppm. The appearance of signals due to the alcoholic proton (singlet, 1H) at δ 2.74 ppm and the methyl protons at δ 3.58 ppm in **3** ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) confirms the presence of coordinated MeOH in **3**. The signal due to the azomethine proton appears at δ 7.03 ppm. This downward shift is indicative of the coordination of N atom of the $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ group²⁹. The appearance of signal due to the enolic proton at δ 13.5 ppm and absence of signal due the N–H proton in **3** ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) indicate the enolization of the keto group during coordination compound formation and non-involvement of the enolic O atom in coordination.

The thermogravimetric analyses of **3** ($M = \text{Zn}$) and **8** indicate that these compounds decompose in two stages. An experimental mass loss of 9.27% (calcd. 9.11%) and 14.56% (calcd. 14.44%) between 80–120 °C, occurring in the above compounds indicates the loss of one and two coordinated MeOH molecules respectively. A steep decrease in weight (between 250–600 °C) attributes to the decomposition of organic skeleton. The plateau obtained after heating the residue above 600 °C corresponds to the formation of metal oxides [ZnO (obsd. = 23.48%, calcd. = 23.16%) and ZrO_2 (obsd. = 27.52%, calcd. = 27.8%)]. These values are in accordance with the proposed formulae for these compounds.

The magnetic moment of **2** is 1.54 B.M. and the lower value is indicative of the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange between two Cu^{II} ions³⁰. The observed magnetic moment values (5.3, 4.3 and 2.5 B.M.) for the dimetallic coordination compounds, $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$, $[\text{Co}(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2]_2$ respectively are lower than the respective spin-only values. The observed lower magnetic moment values are due to the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange between the two metal ions connected by phenoxide bridges. The magnetic moment of **5** is 5.03 B.M. This value is lower than the expected value for high-spin d^5 state ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.92\text{ B.M.}$) and indicates the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange interaction in **5**. The lower magnetic moment value suggests dimerization through the phenolic O atom of LH_3 ^{24,31}. The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the coordination compounds of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zr^{II} , MoO_2^{II} and UO_2^{II} show that they are diamagnetic in nature as expected.

The 3-D molecular modeling of **1**, **3** ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) and **6** have been carried out using hyperchem series of program³². The structures were optimized using molecular mechanics and semiempirical ZINDO/1 (Polak-Ribiere, $\text{RMS} = 0.01 \text{ kcal}$). The energy optimized structures of **1**, **3** ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) and **6** are presented in Figs. 9–11 respectively. The computed structural properties of the above compounds, their selected bond lengths and bond angles

Fig. 9. Energy optimized structure of **1**.

Fig. 10. Energy optimized structure of **3** (where $M = \text{Zn}$).

Fig. 11. Energy optimized structure of **6**.

are listed in Table 2. The geometry optimized model of **1** shows significantly short $[\text{C}(7)=\text{N}(8), 1.32 \text{ \AA}]$ bond length indicating the double bond character between C and N atoms. Also, the $[\text{C}(5)-\text{C}(7), 1.42 \text{ \AA}]$, $[\text{C}(13)-\text{O}(21), 1.32 \text{ \AA}]$ bond lengths are comparable to the reported values³³. The model of **3** ($M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) possesses bond length $[\text{Zn}(1)-\text{O}(4), 2.165 \text{ \AA}]$ and bond angles $[\text{N}(3)-\text{Zn}(1)-\text{O}(4), 100.303^\circ]$, $[\text{O}(2)-\text{Zn}(1)-\text{N}(3), 92.508^\circ]$ comparable to those reported using X-ray crystallography³⁴. The model of **6** possesses $\text{Mo}(1)=\text{O}(2)$ and $\text{Mo}(1)=\text{O}(6)$ bond lengths of 1.78 \AA and 1.75 \AA respectively. The average $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ bond length (1.765 \AA) and bond angle (103.25°) are typical for *cis*- MoO_2 structure³⁵. The average $\text{Mo}-\text{O}$ bond length (2.21 \AA) is relatively larger than $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ bond length due to the greater bond order of $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ than that of $\text{Mo}-\text{O}$. The bond length $[\text{Mo}(1)-\text{N}(5), 2.304 \text{ \AA}]$ and bond angles $[\text{O}(4)-\text{Mo}(1)-\text{N}(5), 76.163^\circ]$; $[\text{N}(5)-\text{Mo}(1)-\text{O}(29), 69.46^\circ]$ are also comparable to the reported values^{35,36}.

Experimental

Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, salicylaldehyde (Sarabhai); cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate, cadmium(II) acetate dihydrate, dioxouranium(VI) acetate tetrahydrate, iron(III) chloride (anhydrous) (BDH); nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (Fluka); copper(II) acetate monohydrate (IDPL); zinc(II) acetate dihydrate (S.D.'s Fine Chemicals); urea (Nice) and *o*-aminophenol (CDH) were used as received for the syntheses. Hexadecaquaoctahydroxotetrairidium(IV) acetate and bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) were synthesized by following the published procedures¹⁶.

Chemical and physical measurements :

The metal contents of the respective coordination compounds were estimated following the standard procedures. CHN analyses were carried out by Eager CHN analyzer model-300. The molar conductance measurements were carried out in DMF with the help of a Toshniwal conductivity bridge (CL01-02A) and a dip type cell calibrated with KCl solutions. The molecular weights of the coordination compounds were determined by the Rast method using diphenyl as the solvent. The IR spectra of **1-8** were recorded in KBr pellets on a Nicolet 5DX FTIR spectrophotometer calibrated with polystyrene. The reflectance spectra of **2**, **4** and **5** were recorded on a Beckman DU

Table 1. Analytical, colour, molar conductance and molecular weight data of compounds

Sr. no.	Compd.	Stoichiometry	Colour	Λ_M (mho cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Mol. wt.	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
						M	C	H	N
1.	1	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	Brown		256 ^a (256)	-	65.48 (65.63)	4.80 (4.69)	10.86 (10.94)
2.	2	Cu ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	Dark-green	3.8	622.2 (635)	19.82 (20.00)	53.07 (52.91)	3.03 (3.15)	8.66 (8.82)
3.	3 (M = Zn ^{II})	ZnC ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	Yellow	8.2	343.8 (351.4)	18.76 (18.61)	51.45 (51.22)	4.11 (3.98)	8.11 (7.97)
4.	3 (M = Cd ^{II})	CdC ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	Brown	6.3	382.8 (398.4)	28.36 (28.21)	45.33 (45.18)	3.43 (3.51)	7.13 (7.03)
5.	4 (M = Mn ^{II})	Mn ₂ C ₃₂ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₁₀	Yellow	2.3	738.4 (745.9)	14.58 (14.73)	51.62 (51.48)	4.75 (4.83)	7.39 (7.51)
6.	4 (M = Co ^{II})	Co ₂ C ₃₂ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₁₀	Yellow	4.5	758.2 (753.9)	15.46 (15.63)	51.12 (50.94)	4.93 (4.78)	7.30 (7.43)
7.	4 (M = Ni ^{II})	Ni ₂ C ₃₂ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₁₀	Brown	5.8	762.8 (753.4)	15.73 (15.58)	50.86 (50.97)	4.62 (4.78)	7.58 (7.43)
8.	5	Fe ₂ C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₈ Cl ₂	Brown	5.5	743.4 (755)	13.97 (14.83)	47.12 (47.68)	3.34 (3.70)	6.98 (7.41)
9.	6	MoC ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆	Dark-yellow	8.6	428.6 (413.9)	23.32 (23.18)	43.65 (43.49)	3.26 (3.38)	6.89 (6.76)
10.	7	UC ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆	Yellow	7.9	548 (556)	42.32 (42.80)	32.12 (32.37)	2.15 (2.52)	4.86 (5.03)
11.	8	ZrC ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₇	Yellow	7.4	437.9 (443.2)	20.73 (20.58)	43.16 (43.32)	4.69 (4.51)	6.47 (6.32)

Abbreviations : ^aMass spectral data.

Table 2. Semiempirical ZINDO/1 computed parameters for compounds

Sr. no.	Compd.	No. of electrons levels	No. of double occupied orbitals	Total orbitals	Total energy (a.u.)	Core-core interaction (kcal/mol)	Heat of formation (kcal/mol)	Selected bond lengths and bond angles
1.	1	96	48	88	-171.1635	412093.08	-6670.092	C(7)=N(8) 1.32 Å; C(9)=O(23) 1.22 Å; C(9)-N(10) 1.32 Å; C(5)-C(7) 1.42 Å; C(4)-O(18) 1.32 Å; C(13)-O(21) 1.32 Å
2.	3 (M = Zn ^{II})	110	55	102	-198.0338	584505.98	-7938.152	Zn(1)-O(4) 2.165 Å; O(2)-Zn(1)-N(3) 92.508°; N(3)-Zn(1)-O(4) 100.303°
3.	6 (M = MoO ₂ ^{II})	126	63	115	-238.0280	722285.16	-7524.915	Mo(1)=O(2) 1.78 Å; Mo(1)=O(6) 1.75 Å; Mo(1)-O(4) 2.13 Å; Mo(1)-N(5) 2.30 Å; O(2)=Mo(1)=O(6) 103.25°; O(4)-Mo(1)-N(5) 76.163°; N(5)-Mo(1)-O(29) 69.46°; O(29)-Mo(1)=O(6) 109.865°

spectrophotometer attached with a reflectance arrangement. The ^1H NMR spectra of **1** and **3** ($\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$) were recorded on Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. The thermogravimetric analysis of the compounds were performed using TGA-50H thermogravimetric analyzer (SHIMADZU) upto $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in N_2 atmosphere. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the standard. The magnetic susceptibility values were corrected for the diamagnetism of metal-ligand system and temperature independent paramagnetism (TIP) terms.

Synthesis of *o*-hydroxyphenylurea (ohypu) : *o*-Aminophenol (10.9 g, 0.1 mol) was dissolved in 20 mL of 1 : 1 HCl. To this solution, urea (24.0 g, 0.4 mol) in small quantity with constant stirring, distilled water (30 mL), HCl (1 mL) and glacial acetic acid (1 mL) were added. The brown solution obtained was refluxed on a water bath for 2 h. The light-brown compound separated on cooling in ice was suction filtered, washed with distilled water and recrystallized from 50% aqueous EtOH and dried *in vacuo*. m.p. = $154\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Yield = 90%; Anal. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: Found (Calcd.)% C = 55.38 (55.26); H = 5.32 (5.26); N = 18.23 (18.42); IR bands : $\nu(\text{N-H})$ (3050 cm^{-1}), $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (carbonyl) (1655 cm^{-1}), $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ (1630 cm^{-1}) and $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) (1520 cm^{-1}).

Synthesis of **1 :** An EtOH solution (50 mL) of *o*-hydroxyphenylurea (15.2 g, 0.1 mol) and salicylaldehyde (12.2 g, 0.1 mol) were refluxed on a water bath for 1 h. The excess of solvent was evaporated and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. The brown compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with EtOH and recrystallized from EtOH and then dried as mentioned above. m.p. = $162\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Yield = 70%; Anal. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: Found (Calcd.)% C = 65.48 (65.63); H = 4.80 (4.69); N = 10.86 (10.94); IR bands : $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (carbonyl) (1669 cm^{-1}), $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) (1620 cm^{-1}), $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) (1526 cm^{-1}).

General method for the syntheses of **2, **3**, **4** and **7** :** A MeOH solution (30 mL) of appropriate metal acetate (5 mmol) was added while constant stirring to a MeOH solution (100 mL) of **1** (1.28 g, 5 mmol). The solution was refluxed on a water bath for 2–3 h and the solid residue separated was suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried as mentioned above. Yield = 50–70%.

Synthesis of **5 :** A MeOH solution (30 mL) of iron(III) chloride (anhydrous) (0.81 g, 5 mmol) was added with constant stirring to a MeOH solution (100 mL) of **1** (1.28 g, 5 mmol). The solution was refluxed for 3 h under anhydrous conditions and the brown solid separated out was suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried as mentioned above. Yield = 53%.

Synthesis of **6 :** A MeOH solution (50 mL) of bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (1.63 g, 5 mmol) was added to a MeOH solution (50 mL) of **1** (1.28 g, 5 mmol). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 h. The yellow solid separated out was suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried as mentioned above. Yield = 75%.

Synthesis of **8 :** A MeOH solution (50 mL) of hexadecaquaoctahydroxotetrazirconium(IV) acetate (5 mmol) was added to a MeOH solution (50 mL) of **1** (1.28 g, 5 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h. A MeOH solution (50 mL) of NaOMe (0.54 g, 10 mmol) was added to the above mixture. The yellow solid obtained was suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried as mentioned above. Yield = 70%.

Conclusion :

The reaction of the dibasic tridentate ONO donor Schiff base (**1**) with different metal ions [Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{III} , MoO_2^{II} , UO_2^{II} and $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2^{\text{II}}$] results in the formation of coordination compounds with different geometries. The coordination compounds [$\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2$] (**2**), [$\text{M}'(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2$] (**4**) ($\text{M}' = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}) and [$\text{FeCl}(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2$] (**5**) are dimetallic having a square-planar (**2**) and an octahedral geometry (**4** and **5**) around the metal ion. The coordination compounds [$\text{M}(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})$] (**3**, **6** and **7**) ($\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , MoO_2^{II} , UO_2^{II}) are monometallic with tetrahedral ($\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II}) (**3**) and octahedral ($\text{M} = \text{MoO}_2^{\text{II}}$ or UO_2^{II}) (**6** and **7**) geometry. The coordination compound [$\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})(\text{MeOH})_2$] (**8**) is monometallic with pentagonal-bipyramidal geometry. The coordination compounds of the Schiff base **1** is quite comparable to those of the isomeric Schiff base derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde and salicylhydrazide.

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